
A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR UNDERSTANDING GPA WITH STUDENTS' EXPERIENCE USING HYBRID ALGORITHM

S. Revathiprabha ^{*1}, Dr. S. Radhimeenakshi ^{*2}

^{*1} M. Phil, Research Scholar, PG & Research Department of Computer Science, Tirupur Kumaran College for Women, Tirupur, Tamil Nadu, India

^{*2} Associate Professor, PG & Research Department of Computer Science, Tiruppur Kumaran College for Women, Tirupur, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract:

Foreseeing understudies' review has risen as a noteworthy zone of examination in training because of the craving to distinguish the fundamental factors that impact scholastic execution. Due to constrained accomplishment in foreseeing the Grade Point Average (GPA), the greater part of the earlier research has concentrated on anticipating grades in a particular arrangement of classes dependent on understudies' earlier exhibitions. The issues related with information driven models of GPA expectation are additionally opened up by a little example measure and a generally vast dimensionality of perceptions in an analysis. In this paper, we use the best in class machine learning systems to develop and approve a prescient model of GPA exclusively dependent on an arrangement of self-administrative learning practices decided in a moderately little example analyze. At last, the objective of level expectation in comparative examinations is to utilize the built models for the outline of mediation methodologies went for helping understudies in danger of scholarly disappointment. In such manner, we lay the numerical preparation for characterizing and identifying most likely accommodating mediations utilizing a probabilistic prescient model of GPA. We exhibit the use of this structure by characterizing fundamental intercessions and recognizing those mediations that are most likely supportive to understudies with a low GPA. The utilization of self-administrative practices is justified, in light of the fact that the proposed mediations can be effortlessly drilled by understudies.

Keywords: GPA; Prediction; Classification; Intervention.

Cite This Article: S. Revathiprabha, and Dr. S. Radhimeenakshi. (2018). "A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH FOR UNDERSTANDING GPA WITH STUDENTS' EXPERIENCE USING HYBRID ALGORITHM." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 5(10), 9-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1473836.

1. Introduction

The main goal of this journal is to find and classify Research Scholar problem in their learning. Track Engineering student's good or bad, situation to complete their Research level experiences. Mining the social media data like engineering students study problems will result to classify the group of Engineering student's according to their experiences and identify their problems to be solved to improve the education quality.

The data collection is made directly mine and analyzes Scholar-posted content with considering the Engineering students problem from uninhibited spaces on the social web with the clear goal of understanding engineering students learning experiences. The existing work has not measured Scholar academic performance to identify the Engineering students problem and classify them accurately for enhancing E-learning experiences.

As a proportion of scholarly execution, one may utilize either class-particular evaluations or review point normal (GPA). In spite of the fact that GPA is by all accounts a more dependable proportion of scholastic execution, its expectation depends intensely on the unwavering quality and consistency of its constituents, i.e., the class-particular evaluations that frame GPA [27]. At the end of the day, substantial contrasts in evaluating measures combined with the measure of elective courses that understudies can take convolutes advance the effectively troublesome issue of GPA expectation.

Chow and Liu [3] set out the foundation for approximating what's more, evaluating the joint likelihood dispersion of a few factors dependent on the rest-arrange reliance tree structure. Up to this point, this model and its variation frame, known as the "Tree Augmented Naive Bayes (TAN)" [7], have been utilized for classification purposes in different applications, counting the classification of hand-printed numerals [3], programming flaw forecast [8], clinical choice help [9], what's more, different discourse and picture handling applications [10],[13]. A few experimental investigations have demonstrated that, in numerous settings, MWDT classifiers can outflank other well known classifiers, for example, credulous Bayes, or, in other words in view of a suspicion of variable freedom [3], [7], [14]. In the meantime, the graphical portrayal given by this model demonstrates the collaboration and any current collaboration among indicators. With the end goal to approve our prescient demonstrate and in the meantime expel the impact of the supposed choice inclination in little example, we use a cross-approval method outer to highlight choice. This technique re-enacts genuine situations where autonomous information would need to be classified after the classifier is fabricated. We additionally evaluate the consistency of every factor in the developed model of GPA forecast.

This paper is sorted out as pursues. Segment II depicts the most extreme weight reliance trees. Segment III presents the component choice and model evaluation. Area IV presents the survey and information accumulation methodology. Segment V displays the developed information driven graphical show for GPA forecast. Area VI talks about efficacy of each factor in foreseeing GPA. In Section VII, we figure the idea of an intercession utilizing our developed model what's more, distinguish those intercessions that are likely useful to understudies with low GPA. At last, finishing up comments are introduced in Section VIII.

2. Most-Extreme Weight Reliance Trees (Mwrt)

First-arrange reliance tree of greatest weight is proposed. To comprehend the working standard of first-arrange reliance tree, consider a vector of arbitrary variables $X=[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p]$ with the likelihood appropriation $\rho(X)$. In this structure, $\rho(x)$, is approximated by a tree reliance circulation $\rho_{Tree}(X)$ that is gotten by result of $p - 1$ sets astute restrictive likelihood.

$$pTree(x) = \prod_{i=1}^p p(x_i|x_{m_i})(1)$$

where x_{m_i} is the "parent" of x_i , $m_1 \triangleq 0$, $(m_2, \dots, m_p)$ is an incarnation of an unknown subset of integers $\{2, 3, \dots, P\}$, and $P(x_1|x_0) \triangleq P(x_1)$. We assume that $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p$ are ranked in such a way that $m_i < i$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, P$. A tree is then a graph that is uniquely defined by a P -tuple $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_p)$ where the i -th component of $\mathbf{m}$ shows the parent of variable x_i . To construct the graph, we can assign a node to variable x_i and an edge from x_i to x_{m_i} . The information theoretic distance measure, the Kullback-Leibler cross-entropy for discrete variables, to assess the goodness of similar to $P(X)$ by $P_{Tree}(X)$. In this regard, they attempted to find the tree dependence structure τ such that.

$$D_{KL}(P(X)||P_{\tau}(X)) \leq D_{KL}(P(X)||P_{Tree}(X)), \forall Tree \in$$

where T_p is the position of all probable tree reliance structure of p nodes such that $m_i < i$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, p$, and

$$D_{KL}(P(X)||P_{Tree}(X)) = \sum_x \frac{P(X)}{P_{Tree}(X)}$$

3. Feature Selection and Model Assessment

Perchance the most critical part of any classifier is its disentanglement mistake, characterized as the possibility of misclassification, since it measures the prophetic limit of the classifier. On the off chance that examples are substantial, at that point some portion of the information can be waited for mistake estimation. In any case, when the quantity of accessible example indicates is equivalent in size the quantity of potential factors that can be utilized in the classifier, both the classification and mistake estimation rules are connected to a similar arrangement of preparing data a circumstance that we look in the present examination. In the meantime, it is the general accord that the execution of a built classifier does not continue enhancing as more highlights (factors) are added to the model. This wonder is known as the scourge of dimensionality, or the cresting marvel. This phenomenon upholds the strategy of the component selection to be connected.

Once an element determination technique is connected, it is fundamental to assess the execution of each component subset. In such manner, cross-approval (CV) is a typical evaluation technique. In any case, to maintain a strategic distance from inclination determination, which results in an idealistic forecast mistake of the last built classifier, it is basic to apply the cross-approval system outer to the component choice advance. In this work, we have connected this methodology to get a sensible perspective of forecast mistake.

4. Questionnaire, Data Collection, and Preprocessing

Goldman and Slaughter contended that since understudies in a particular office generally take classes inside their own significant fields, the GPA level of understudies selected in various offices can have an alternate scale. As such, a few offices may give higher evaluations than others do

notwithstanding for a similar level of execution situation that can conceivably Undermine the legitimacy of the GPA metric. With the end goal to maintain a strategic distance from this issue, we arranged and circulated a 20-question overview among second-to fourth-year understudies selected just in the electrical designing system at Nazar bayev University. The study was led for multi week utilizing Qualtrics, where 82 understudies reacted. The gathered information and the appropriation of reactions are displayed in the Supplementary Table S1 and Table S2, separately. For the review, we received and redid eighteen inquiries from that as we would like to think bargain most specifically with inquiry.

- Q1. Do you permit time for exercise and associating with companions?
- Q2. Do you get somewhere around 60 long stretches of rest every night?
- Q3. Do you learn no less than 2 hours for each hour of class?
- Q4. Do you have a region where you generally go to think about?
- Q5. Is your examination zone free of commotion and diversions and agreeable?
- Q6. Can you contemplate for in any event 30 minutes without getting up taking bite or Telephone breaks?
- Q7. Do you utilize your opportunity between classes to examine?
- Q8. Do you begin inspecting for real exams somewhere around 3 days ahead of time?
- Q9. How frequently do you realize that kinds of inquiries will be on the test?
- Q10. Are you ready to complete your tests in the permitted timeframe?
- Q11. Do you get your work done issues and assignments without taking a gander at the arrangements?
- Q12. Do you make inquiries in classes when you don't comprehend an idea?
- Q13. Are you ready to take notes in classes, stay aware of the educator and comprehend the ideas at the occasionally?
- Q14. Do you survey your notes after each class, ideally directly after classes?
- Q15. Do you make notes and feature them as you read class materials at home?
- Q16. Can you read and advance at the rate of 12-15 pages for each hour for history compose material?
- Q17. Can you focus and comprehend the material you read without re-perusing a second or third time?
- Q18. Do you modify your perusing styles when you are considering for writing, sociology or science classes?
- Q19. In which of the accompanying time interims do you normally think about?
- Q20. What is your aggregate GPA out of 4.00?

The understudies were solicited to demonstrate their degree from concurrence with each inquiry: I) generally; II) more often than not; III) now and then; IV) rarely. For only Q₁₉, the available choices were the following: I) 0:00-6:00, II) 6:01-12:00, III) 12:01-18:00, or IV) 18:01-23:59. In our study, the entire set of questions in the questionnaire, i.e., Q₁ to Q₁₉, form the set of potential random variable that can be used in the structure of the final constructed predictive model (through feature-selection process); to wit, each x_i in (1) is one of the questions among Q₁ to Q₁₉. This set of questions as a group take on values in a finite state of $b = 4^{19} > 2 \times 10^{11}$ possible states. At the same time, an upper bound on the number of states with an available measurement in our dataset is only 82 (responders) $\times$ 4 (options) = 328. The same procedure has been applied to Q₁₉to

combine study hours 0:00-6:00 with 6:01-12:00 (to form group A), and combine hours 12:01-18:00 with 18:01-23:59 (to form group B).

5. Model Construction and Validation

We connected a thorough look utilizing a wrapper approach for highlight subset choice. In such manner, the prescient capacity of each of the $2^{19}-1=524,288$ conceivable element subsets is assessed utilizing the MWDT structure and a 10-foldcross-approval. The last build MWRDT association is the classifier with the most elevated exactness amidst all subsets of highlights. This more tasteful, or, in other words Figure 3, is completely described by the restrictive probabilities between hubs displayed in the Supplementary Table S3. Out of 19 potential factors that were a piece of our overview (see Table 1), the built more tasteful utilizes 10 factors recognized by, $Q_2, Q_7, Q_9, Q_{10}, Q_{12}, Q_{13}, Q_{15}, Q_{17}, Q_{18},$ and Q_{19} and Denoting genuine positive, genuine negative, false positive, and false negative, by TP, TN, FP, and FN, individually, the perplexity grid acquired by rooting substitution exactness estimator is displayed For this situation, the precision of the model estimated by $(TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP)$ is 82%. In any case, this extent of exactness is an over optimistic estimator. To have a functional point of view of the farsighted exactness of the model, we associated the outside cross-endorsement system separated in Section III. Presents the perplexity organize gotten by applying the external cross-endorsement system. In like way, the model has an exactness of 65.85% with an affectability $TP/(TP+FN)$ of 63.9% and a determine city $TP/(FP+TN)$ of 67.4%.

6. Efficacy of Each Unpredictable in Judicious A High And Low GPA

In this area, we look to rank the components that are parts of our "GPA arrange" in light of their consistency. To formalize the thought, let $Q_i, \psi_{\mathcal{F}'|F}, \Psi$, and $\hat{\epsilon}(\psi_{\mathcal{F}'|F})$, denote a variable, the classifier constructed with the set of variables $\mathcal{F}'$ out of initial set of variables $\mathcal{F}$ in the dataset, the classification rule Ψ (here wrapper feature selection with MWDT) applied to an initial set of variables $\mathcal{F}$, and the accuracy estimate of the classifier $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'|F}$, respectively.

In other words, $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'|F}$ is a result of Ψ applying to the dataset. Note that when $\mathcal{F}'$ contains only one single variable, e.g., $\mathcal{F}' = \{Q_i\}$, the constructed MWDT network on the dataset with variables $\mathcal{F}$ reduces to discrete histogram rule there is no other variable to be used in conjunction with Q_i in the tree structure. The coefficient of determination (CoD) has been extended to and used in classification, to find and rank variable(s):

$$\text{CoD} = \frac{\hat{\epsilon}(\psi_{Q_i|F}) - \hat{\epsilon}(\psi_0|F)}{\hat{\epsilon}(\psi_{Q_i|F})}$$

CoP measures the relative increase in the classification accuracy by using the full set $\mathcal{F}$ in comparison with the set $\mathcal{F} - Q_i$ obtained by omitting Q_i from $\mathcal{F}$. In order to find $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'_i|F}$, we apply the classification rule Ψ to the set of variables $\mathcal{F}$, which generally results in a classifier constructed on a lower dimensional space $\mathcal{F}'$. Instead, to construct $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'_i|F - Q_i}$, we apply the same classification rule Ψ to the set of variables $\mathcal{F} - Q_i$, which results in a classifier constructed

generally on a different set of variables than $\mathcal{F}'$, namely, $\mathcal{F}'_i$. With the end goal to abstain from overfitting, we expect we are ignorant concerning the arrangement of factors chose as a component of the GPA organize. At the end of the day, we accept $\mathcal{F}$ is the full arrangement of factors in the first dataset. In other words, for our situation,

$$\mathcal{F}' = \{Q_2, Q_7, Q_9, Q_{10}, Q_{12}, Q_{13}, Q_{15}, Q_{17}, Q_{18}, Q_{19}\},$$

$$\mathcal{F} = \cup_{i=1}^{19} \{Q_i\}$$

and each time we remove a variable from $\mathcal{F}$, we apply the full external cross-validation (as described in Section III) to assess the performance of a newly constructed classifier $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'_i} | \mathcal{F} - Q_i$. At the same time, applying an exhaustive wrapper feature selection procedure, as we have done in Section III, guarantees that which leads to $\text{CoP} \geq 0$. The inequality (11) holds because the initial feature set $\mathcal{F}$ to construct $\psi(\mathcal{F}' | \mathcal{F})$ contains one more feature than the initial set of features $\mathcal{F} - Q_i$ that leads to $\psi_{\mathcal{F}'_i} | \mathcal{F} - Q_i$. Therefore, using an exhaustive search leads to a an equal or smaller error of $\psi(\mathcal{F}' | \mathcal{F})$ than $\mathcal{F}'_i | \mathcal{F} - Q_i$. The accuracy of the GPA network depicted in $\hat{\epsilon}\psi(\mathcal{F}' | \mathcal{F}) = 65:85\%$, is also an upper bound on $\hat{\epsilon}(\psi_{\mathcal{F}'_i} | \mathcal{F} - Q_i), \forall i$, and as a result we have $0 \leq \text{CoP} \leq 1$.

7. Intervention Strategy

An advantage of using the MWDT structure, which is essentially a Bayesian network united for learning in small-sample situations, is its translatability into intervention strategies. In order to mathematically formalize an intervention strategy, we define an observed set of evidence e_O to be a set of answers given by a student to a set of questions from the GPA model.

$$e_O = \{(Q_i, q_i) | Q_i \in \mathcal{F}', q_i \in \{A, B\}\}$$

Where $\mathcal{F}'$ is the set of all variables in the classifier (in our case obtained from (9)), and A and B are the reformed categories of answers as described in Section IV. Similarly, let e_T be a set of testable evidence based on the set of questions in e_O that might help the student to improve the GPA.

Proof: For a fixed e_O with cardinality $n \leq p$, there are $\binom{n}{m}$ interventions of order $m < n$ where $1 \leq m \leq n$. Therefore, for this fixed e_O , there exist $\sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m}$ potential interventions of order $m < n$. Note that there are 2^n possible set of observed evidence e_O of cardinality n . This means that there are in total $(2^n - 1) \times 2^n$ potential interventions of order $m < n$ for all possible e_O of cardinality n . Since n can be any integer from 1 to p , there are in total $\sum_{n=1}^p (2^{2^n} - 2^n)$ potential interventions and the result follows.

In our case where the GPA network includes 10 variables (see Fig. 3), Lemma1 Suggests the existence of 1,396,054 possible interventions. A detailed characterization and description of these many interventions is not simply possible. However, in order to display the submission of the aforesaid framework to define and become aware of the set of probably helpful interventions, we

only consider the set of interventions of order $1 < 1$. Lemma 2 characterize an appealing material goods of intervention of arrange $1 < 1$.

$$FPP_{e_{T|e_0}} = \frac{P(GPA=H|\{(Q_i,B)\})}{P(GPA=L|\{(Q_i,A)\})} > 1$$

At the same time, note that we have,

$$P(GPA = H | \{(Q_i, B)\}) + P(GPA = L | \{(Q_i, B)\}) = 1$$

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File Edit View Navigate Source Refactor Run Debug Profile Team Tools Window Help
<default config>
Output - GPA Prediction (run)
cod==== 12 : 0.8
cod==== 1 : 0.8
cod==== 7 : 0.7777777777777777
cod==== 2 : 0.8378378378378379
cod==== 8 : 0.7272727272727274
cod==== 17 : 0.6470588235294118
cod==== 3 : 0.8378378378378379
cod==== 9 : 0.8378378378378379
cod==== 13 : 0.8378378378378379
cgp==== 0 : 0.0
cgp==== 4 : 0.0
cgp==== 5 : 0.0
cgp==== 10 : 0.0
cgp==== 12 : 0.0
cgp==== 1 : 0.0
cgp==== 7 : 0.0
cgp==== 2 : 0.0
cgp==== 8 : 0.0
cgp==== 17 : 0.0
cgp==== 3 : 0.0
cgp==== 9 : 0.0
cgp==== 13 : 0.0
sdp = 0 = 0.5070422535211268
sdp = 4 = 0.24295774647887325
sdp = 5 = 0.25704225352112675
sdp = 10 = 0.75
sdp = 12 = 0.25704225352112675
sdp = 1 = 0.5
sdp = 7 = 0.24295774647887325
sdp = 2 = 0.25
sdp = 8 = 0.007042253521126751
sdp = 17 = 0.007042253521126751
sdp = 3 = 0.25
sdp = 9 = 0.5070422535211268
sdp = 13 = 0.25
BUILD SUCCESSFUL (total time: 7 seconds)

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GPA Prediction in J48

References

- [1] Dr. S. Radhimeenakshi, Ms. S.Revathiprabha “ An Outlook Inquire For Better Excellence In Learning Regulation For Assessment” Volume 5(2), ISSN: 2394-9333 pp: 562-653, International Journal of Trend in Research and Development.
- [2] Dr. S. Radhimeenakshi, Ms. S.Revathiprabha “ Appointment Ruler Exclusive Of Multiple Techno Decision Trees Reflection Towards Recital For Employability” Vol.5 (Iss.3): March, 2018 ISSN: 2454-1907 page no: 257-262, International Journal of Engineering and Technologies and Management Research.
- [3] C. K. Chow and C. N. Liu, “Approximating discrete probability distributions with dependence trees,” IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory, vol. 14, no. 3 pp. 462_467, May 1968.
- [4] N. Friedman, D. Geiger, and M. Goldszmidt, “Bayesian network classifiers,” Mach. Learn., vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 131_163, Nov. 1997.
- [5] K. Dejaeger, T. Verbraken, and B. Baesens, “Toward comprehensible software fault prediction models using Bayesian network classifiers,” IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng., vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 237_257, Feb. 2013.

- [6] M. B. Sesen, A. E. Nicholson, R. Banares-Alcantara, and M. Brady, "Bayesian networks for clinical decision support in lung cancer care," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 8, no. 12, p. e82349, 2013.
- [7] X. Zhu and D. Ramanan, "Face detection, pose estimation, and landmark localization in the wild," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.*, Jun. 2012, pp. 2879_2886.
- [8] V. Y. F. Tan, S. Sanghavi, J. W. Fisher, and A. S. Willsky, "Learning graphical models for hypothesis testing and classification," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 5481_5495, Nov. 2010.
- [9] S. Tschiatschek and F. Pernkopf, "On Bayesian network classifiers with reduced precision parameters," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 774_785, Apr. 2015.
- [10] R. Mottaghi, S. Fidler, A. Yuille, R. Urtasun, and D. Parikh, "Humanmachine CRFs for identifying bottlenecks in scene understanding," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 74_87, Jan. 2016.
- [11] M. G. Madden, "On the classification performance of TAN and general Bayesian networks," *Knowl.-Based Syst.*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 489_495, Oct. 2009.
- [12] G. McLachlan, *Discriminant Analysis and Statistical Pattern Recognition*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 2004. K. Jain and W. G. Waller, "On the optimal number of features in the classification of multivariate Gaussian data," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 10, nos. 5_6, pp. 365_374, 1978.
- [13] G. J. McLachlan, "The bias of the apparent error rate in discriminant analysis," *Biometrika*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 239_244, 1976.
- [14] C. Ambrose and G. J. McLachlan, "Selection bias in gene extraction on the basis of microarray gene-expression data," *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, vol. 99, no. 10, pp. 6562_6566, 2002.
- [15] V. N. Gordon, P. Royster, and T. L. Minnich, "University survey: A guidebook and readings for new students," *Ohio State Univ., Columbus, OH, USA, Tech. Rep.*, 2000.
- [16] (2017). *Grade In_ation at American Colleges and Universities*. [Online]. Available: http://www.gradein_ation.com/
- [17] R. Kohavi and G. H. John, "Wrappers for feature subset selection," *Artif. Intell.*, vol. 97, nos. 1_2, pp. 273_324, 1997.
- [18] R. O. Duda, P. E. Hart, and D. G. Stork, *Pattern Classi_cation*, 2nd ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2001.